

Mulching and soil health

Mulching is the practice of covering the surface of the soil with plant material or other natural means, with the goal of protecting the crops and improving the soil. It is divided into living such as cover plants (rye, clover) and dead (mulch) ground cover (straw, leaves, grass clippings, crop residues, and natural: tree bark (spruce) after fertilization, tree leaves, organic residues).

ESTABLISHMENT DESCRIPTION AND BENEFITS

In living mulching, cover crops are planted after the harvest of the main crop or among crop rows in the case of being woody perennials the main crop. Cover crop species selection, termination stage and method need careful planning, as every crop cultivation facility has its own needs like nutrient accessibility, sufficient biomass, organic matter and pest protection, while also considering the geographical and climate circumstances that limit the cultivation of certain crop species. The cover crop is terminated before the next planting by mowing and soil incorporation enhancing soil fertility or the use of herbicides that may hinder soil health. In dead mulching, the soil is covered with plant residues remaining after harvest. The residues are cut or chopped and evenly distributed on the soil surface or lightly incorporated into the soil, depending on the cultivation system. In external natural mulching tree bark is usually shredded or in chips and like residues can be distributed on the surface or into the soil, the harvesting and incorporation should also not be near trunks to prevent rot. Mulching directly affects

the key indicators of soil health such as the protection against soil and wind erosion, improved water retention, enhancement of soil life, increase in organic matter, temperature regulation, weed suppression and pest control.

Figure 1. Soil cover by crop residues (Photo Vasiliki Lappa, 2025)

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

The species to be used for weed control must produce a large plant mass as their remains can cover a large surface area, while not creating problems to the next crop as some allelopathic properties may inhibit the germination and growth of the next crop.

KEYWORDS

mountainous soil health, cover plants, weeds, crops

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